

USING COPING STRATEGIES TO SOLVE PROBLEMS AS A STUDENT

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Abstract

This article provides information about coping strategies during the student period and analyzes theoretical information about coping strategies. Also, the results of the research conducted on students are explained.

Key words

coping strategies, problematic issues, problem solving, resilience, social support, problem avoidance.

Enter.

One of the most urgent problems of today is to dramatically increase the efficiency in the education of the young generation. Because the development, progress and prospects of our Republic depend more on the skills of young professionals trained by schools of general education and higher education. Therefore, it is desirable to use advanced, active methods of teaching, to use reasonable tools. In this context, it is one of the important tasks to overcome the difficulties in acquiring knowledge and achieve quality education of students by learning different coping strategies for solving life problems.

students' coping strategies, we should first familiarize ourselves with the general explanations of coping strategies in problematic issues.

The main part.One of the ways to come up with problem solving is coping strategies and being able to use the most effective ones. Coping strategies can be useful in one situation and completely ineffective in another, the same strategy can be useless in another and useless in another, and such a coping strategy is considered effective if it improves the situation of the person when using them.

a coping strategy depends on many factors. First of all, it has clear information about the individuality of the subject and the characteristics that caused the behavior to overcome the situation. In addition, gender and age, social, cultural and other characteristics may have different effects [4, 623]

Resilience is a characteristic of an integral that includes three relatively autonomous components: participation, control and risk. High-resilience subjects use the most effective coping strategies to overcome stress (problem-solving planning, positive reappraisal), while those with lower resilience use less effective coping strategies (distancing, avoidance/avoidance).

Studies have allowed experts to recognize problem-solving planning and positive reappraisal strategies as more flexible, contributing to problem solving, and less flexible in distance and flight/escape. The obtained results made it possible to confirm the hypothesis of a positive relationship between resilience and its components: overcoming, planning a solution to the problem and using negative strategies, using coping strategies, distance and avoidance strategies.

It is necessary to study through positive re-evaluation. This can be explained by the fact that, as experts say, this type of struggle implies a philosophical approach to negative events and leads to rejection of an effective solution to the problem. Therefore, positive reappraisal may be more effective for older people than for students.

The block of behavioral coping styles "seeking support" reflects the versatility of behavioral methods and allows the use of available social resources. The content of seeking help depends on its meaning (appeal, repentance), source (family, friends), its type (emotional, financial, instrumental) and scope of search (study, medicine) reflects. [3, 20]

The fact that there are many coping strategies does not mean that a person will use one of them. Following R. Lazarus and S. Folkman and K. Garver, we can assume that in a certain situation a person, depending on his personal characteristics and the nature of the situation, turns to a whole set of coping strategies, i.e. One of the central questions of the theory of coping by R. Lazarus and S. Folkman is the issue of its dynamics. According to the authors, coping is a dynamic process with structural components, i.e. coping is not permanent, but can be modified when social conditions change.[2, 214]

Coping is a multidimensional process of cognitive and behavioral strategies that people use to manage demands in specific stressful situations.

The issue of the dynamics of getting out of the problem is directly related to the problem of predicting the behavior of this or that person in a stressful situation.

The social content of the problem-solving process, that is, the specific features of the event with which a person interacts during the coping process, can affect the coping process. The situation mainly determines the logic of people's behavior and the level of responsibility for the result of their actions. The characteristics of the

situation determine the behavior to a greater extent than the location of the subject. Stressful situations have a significant impact on a person's behavior.

Behavior is mainly determined not by an objective given situation, but by its subjective evaluation and perception, but the objective indicators of the situation reflected in the subjective representation of the person cannot be taken into account.

R. Lazarus offers two forms of assessment - primary and secondary. During the initial assessment, a person evaluates his resources, in other words, answers the following question: "What do I need to do to cope with this situation?" The answer to this question contributes to the quality of his emotional reactions and their intensity. In secondary appraisal, a person evaluates his possible actions and predicts the response actions of the environment. In other words, it asks the following questions: "What can I do? What is my coping strategy? And how will the environment respond to my actions?" The response affects the type of coping strategy chosen to manage the stressful situation .[2,213]

The role of the ability to assess the situation is important, it depends on the adequate choice of coping strategies. The nature of the assessment largely depends on a person's belief in the ability to control the situation and change it. The term "Cognitive assessment" is included in the science, which defines a specific activity of a person, that is, it consists in recognizing the characteristics of the situation, determining its negative and positive aspects, and determining the meaning and importance of what is happening.

The strategies that a person uses to solve a difficult situation depend on how a person's knowledge evaluation mechanism works. The result of cognitive evaluation can be reflected in a person's conclusion about whether he can solve the given situation or not, whether he can control the course of events, or whether the situation is beyond his control. If the subject feels that the situation is under control, he will tend to use constructive coping strategies to deal with it

Discussions and results: The study experimental in the study of coping strategies in students 116 with 119 students majoring in foreign languages and 116 majoring in history psychodiagnostic event stake there was _

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Table 1

Statistical analysis according to the Kolmogorov Smirnov criterion

Indicators	Kolmogorov Smirnov Z	P confidence level
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The problemelimination _	4,818	0.000 *
Socialk o' mak	1,639	.009 **
From the problemescape	1,855	.002 **

In order to study students' coping strategies, we conducted D. Amir Khan's methodology for studying coping strategies for overcoming life problems [1,106]. Accordingly, we checked the Kolmogorov-Smirnov criterion in order to determine whether the obtained data correspond to the law of normal distribution or not. Data on the Problem Solving Scale

We observed that it did not correspond to the law of normal distribution. ($Z=4.818$; $p<0.001$)

In the following analysis, we use nonparametric criteria (Mann Whitney, Wilcoxon, Kruskal Wallis and Spearman).

We observed that the data on the social support scale did not conform to the Normal distribution law. ($Z=1.639$; $p<0.01$) In the following analysis, we use nonparametric criteria (Mann Whitney, Wilcoxon, Kruskal Wallis and Spearman). We also observed that the data for the problem_avoidance scale did not conform to the Normal distribution law. ($Z=1.855$; $p<0.01$) In the following analysis, we use nonparametric criteria (Mann Whitney, Wilcoxon, Kruskal Wallis and Spearman).

Table 2

Amir Khan Differences in the Methodology of Coping Strategies by Specialties

(n= 351 based on the Kruskal Wallis test)

	Expertise	N	Average color	H	P
Troubleshooting	foreign language	116	129.78	37,262	0.000***
	Mathematics	119	194.44		
	History	116	203.31		
	Total:	351			
Social support	foreign language	116	146.48	23,743	0.000***
	Mathematics	119	171.09		
	History	116	210.55		
	Total:	351			
Avoiding the problem	Foreign language	116	150.63	15,929	0.000***
	Mathematics	119	174.02		
	History	116	203.41		
	Total:	351			

Figure 1

From the analysis of the results of Amir Khan's method of studying coping strategies for overcoming life problems, it was found that the results of students studying foreign languages, mathematics and history of three types of majors were invisible in the analysis of the indicators of the scale of Problem Solving, until the history major was invisible. a high result was observed in students ($H = 37,262$; $p < 0.001$) ,In the scale of social support, the same result was obtained, that is, the students studying in the specialty of history received more indicators. ($H=23.743$; $p < 0.001$) , we saw that the results of history students were also high on the problem avoidance strategy scale ($H=15.929$; $p < 0.001$) . When using coping strategies, history students always take into account the situation and circumstances. It was found out that they do not always use the same strategies, but they do everything in their place, research has also revealed that, as long as young people do not follow exactly one strategy during the student period , they are adults. When they are still young children, they solve their problems on their own without consulting anyone, and sometimes they rely on the help of their relatives. -they try to parents, parents know that they always use them.

Summary.

In conclusion, since students can be in different psychiatry, teaching students to solve life problems involves considering the following:

1. In order to effectively implement educational processes in higher and general educational institutions, it is necessary to have a continuous influence between students and teachers. At the basis of the cooperation between the teacher and the student is the problem of correct implementation of educational work.

Since this problem has been very little researched in the field of family education school psychology, it is appropriate to think more widely about the same problem.

2. One of the main characteristics of the student period is the rapid realization of social maturity. It is known that social maturity (maturity) requires a person to have the necessary mental abilities and prepare to take on various roles in social life (building a family), raising a child, participating in useful work (working in a responsible role).

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